

Optical simulations of stray light on instrumented baffles surrounding Virgo end mirrors during O5

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February 21, 2023

Abstract

As part of the second phase of the upgrade program of Advanced Virgo, instrumented baffles are being constructed to be installed around the end mirrors in the main Fabry-Perot cavities, in continuation of what has been implemented for the input mode cleaner end mirror during phase I. According to the current design, these baffles will be equipped with more than 200 photosensors, allowing for real-time monitoring of the stray light around the mirrors. We present optical simulations of the light distribution in the detector's main cavities to assess the ability of the sensors to effectively monitor the presence of defects in the mirrors' surface and to play a role in the pre-alignment of the interferometer.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6815439

Introduction

Advanced Virgo is a gravitational wave detector that takes the form of a dual-recycled Fabry-Perot-Michelson interferometer with 3 km-long orthogonal arms located in Cascina, Italy [1]. It has taken part in two observing runs since 2017, conjointly with the two LIGO detectors in the United States, which have resulted in the detection of more than 90 gravitational-wave signals from compact binary coalescences so far. The detector is regularly upgraded between observing runs to reduce noise and increase its overall sensitivity. The current and next phases of upgrades should allow Virgo to reach its design sensitivity during the O5 run, expected in 2024-2025.

Stray light is one of the main sources of noise in the detector. Because of small imperfections in the optical cavity, a fraction of the light is scattered away from the main axis. In addition to decreasing the power circulating in the cavity, a part of this light may recombine into the main beam, adding a spurious phase information that spoils the sensitivity of the detector. To mitigate this effect, passive baffles are placed at strategic locations in the tube, in the core optics and around the main mirrors. These anti-reflexive surfaces allow to absorb 99.5% of stray light.

In order to monitor stray light in real time, the Virgo experiment plans to equip the baffles surrounding the end mirror (EM) in the main arms with photosensors. These instrumented baffles will provide information on the distribution of scattered light at low angles with the aim of helping with pre-alignment, detecting the presence of defects on the mirrors, and monitoring the development of higher order modes in the laser beam. A first instrumented baffle was installed in 2021 around the EM of the input mode cleaner (IMC), as a way to demonstrate the technology and prepare the

installation around the main mirrors. This baffle has 76 sensors and is currently operational. The first measurements are described in ref. [2], and are consistent with simulations previously realised [3].

The optical simulations presented here are intended to assess the merits of instrumented baffles around the main mirrors and provide specifications for the realisation of the instrument. We notably compute the amount of power received by the sensors in different configurations, introducing imperfections in the cavity such as misalignment and point defects on the mirrors, and estimate the ability of the sensors to detect such defects.

Principle of the simulations

The planned layout of the instrumented baffle is shown in Fig. 1. It consists in 3 concentric rings of 72 sensors located at 27, 28, and 29 cm from the mirror's center. Two other rings of sensors at 30 and 31 cm should be populated by 24 and 12 sensors, respectively. The sensors will be similar to the ones used for the IMC baffle, which are SI-based photodiodes with an active area of 0.49 cm^2 provided by the Hamamatsu company in Japan. The final layout and characteristics of the sensors may be subject to modifications due to technical constraints or the potential effect of the baffles on the overall sensitivity of the detector.

We simulate the distribution of light in a Virgo main arm using the Stationary Interferometer Simulation software (SIS) [4]. SIS is an FFT-based code that computes the propagation of the field in a resonating cavity, taking into account realistic elements such as mirror surface maps, thermal deformations, and coating absorption. A scheme of the optical system simulated is presented in Fig. 2. The effect of the cryobaffle located at 5.4 m from the EM is taken into account by clipping the field at a radius of 30 cm. The output of the simulation is the 2D distribution of the field on a grid,

Figure 1: Planned design of the instrumented baffle surrounding the EM.

computed at the level of the mirrors. Fig. 3 shows the distribution of power around the EM obtained in nominal configuration, i.e for a perfectly aligned cavity with realistic mirror maps. For the input

mirror (IM) the mirror map used is derived from actual measurements realised in O3. Since the EM will be changed before O5, we use a simulated mirror map. For practical purposes, we define 5 rings of 72 sensors and integrate the surface power over the active area to compute the power seen by each sensor. We show these results in Fig. 4. In average, sensors located between 27 and 30 cm from the center of the mirror would see a power of 10^{-4} W. The angular distribution of power is non-isotropic and has a large variance due to the scattering from imperfect mirrors.

Figure 2: Sketch of the optical system simulated that represents a single Virgo arm. The power of the beam impinging on the input mirror (IM) is 1.36 kW, which corresponds to the expected value for O5 after the power recycling cavity. Baffles are represented in dark grey, and mirrors in light grey.

Misalignment

We simulate a misaligned cavity by tilting the EM around the vertical axis. The main consequence of such misalignment is a loss of power in the cavity, and the development of higher order modes in the beam, decreasing the sensitivity of the detector. For a tilt angle of $0.1 \mu\text{rad}$, the power in the cavity decreases by 5%, while for an angle of $1 \mu\text{rad}$, it drops by more than 90%.

As shown in Fig. 5, misalignment induces an excess of power in the sensors in the direction where the beam is shifted, which is more pronounced in the rings that are closer to the center. In order to monitor this effect, we define the observable quantity ΔP , which is the difference of power seen by opposite sensors on the baffle. This variable has therefore 0 mean and a given variance σ , which is computed over all sensors populating a given ring, allowing to define a signal to noise ratio $\Delta P/\sigma$.

Figure 3: Map of the surface power distribution on the EM in nominal configuration (perfectly aligned cavity and realistic mirror maps). The black and red circles indicate the inner and outer radius of the baffle, respectively. White disks represent the sensors on the baffle surrounding the mirror.

The angular distribution of this SNR is shown in Fig. 6 for a tilt angle of $0.3 \mu\text{rad}$. The peak in the direction $\phi = \pi$ is characteristic of a misalignment.

We find that the first ring of sensors at 27 cm from the center of the EM would allow to detect misalignment in the cavity characterized by tilt angles in the range $0.2 - 0.5 \mu\text{rad}$. When the misalignment becomes larger, the power circulating in the cavity decreases sharply to the point that it becomes out of resonance. In this case, sensors in the inner rings will receive up to 1 W of power, which will lead them to saturate. However, sensors in the outer ring at 31 cm, who are "hidden" from the beam by the cryobaffle in nominal configuration, would be able to detect some light in this configuration. Therefore, they may provide useful information for pre-alignment operations.

Point absorbers

Point absorbers (PA) are small (smaller than the beam size) highly absorbing areas that may be present on the mirrors. Several of them have been detected in both Virgo and the two LIGO detectors during the third observing run [5]. Their origin seems to be linked to a high concentration of aluminium on the mirror, which makes them difficult to clean. These PAs are harmful to the sensitivity of the detector, as they scatter power from the fundamental resonating mode of the beam into higher order modes, decreasing the overall circulating power. In order to detect these defects, one needs to physically inspect the mirrors, which is impractical, and cannot be done during observations. That is why we are interested in assessing the ability of instrumented baffles to monitor them.

We simulate the presence of a PA in SIS by adding a 50 mW absorbing point at 1 cm to the right

Figure 4: Power seen by each sensor in nominal configuration. Values for are displayed for each ring as a function of the radial angle ϕ . The power in the fifth ring is significantly lower than in the first four ones because the cryobaffle clips the field at a radius of 30 cm.

Figure 5: Power seen by sensors for a tilt angle of 0.3 μ rad (left) and 0.8 μ rad (right). The direction of the tilt is $\phi = \pi$.

Figure 6: Distribution of the SNR of ΔP as a function of the sensor's angular position and distance to the center of the mirror, in the case where the EM is tilted by $0.3 \mu\text{rad}$.

of the center of the EM. We show in Fig. 7 the angular distribution of power for sensors on each ring in this configuration. The presence of the PA affects the radial distribution of power, with sensors at larger radii seeing more power than sensors closer to the mirror. This behaviour is clearly different from what we observe in the nominal case, where absorption by the mirror's surface is uniform, and for a misaligned cavity. In that regard, the sensors are able to tell the presence of a 50 mW PA on the mirror's surface. Additional work will be required to quantify the minimal absorbing power that is detectable, and determine whether the precise position of a PA can be inferred from the sensors' output.

Conclusions

We have conducted optical simulations of stray light in order to assess the merits of an instrumented baffle around the EM, notably its ability to monitor misalignment in the cavity and the presence of point absorbers on the mirror. The main conclusions of this study are the following:

- The order of magnitude of the power seen by each sensor is 10^{-4} W.
- Sensors are able to detect a tilt of the EM of 2×10^{-7} rad or more.
- The direction of misalignment can be inferred from the output of the sensors.
- Point absorbers generate more scattered light at large angles.
- A 50 mW point absorber near the EM center can be detected, but we cannot infer its precise position.

Therefore, these instrumented baffles should provide helpful information for pre-alignment operations and the correction of potential misalignment. Although the exact position of point absorbers may not be inferred, the sensors will allow for real-time monitoring of scattered light at low angles and therefore the detection of potential contamination on the mirrors. This work will be completed by a study of the effect of the instrumented baffle on the final sensitivity curve of Virgo, taking into account the potential backscattering from the sensors into the cavity. [5]

Figure 7: Power seen by sensors on different rings in the case where a 50 mW point absorber is located at 1 cm to the right of the EM.

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